

ENHANCING DECARBONIZATION AND ACHIEVING ZERO EMISSIONS IN INDUSTRIES AND MANUFACTURING PLANTS: A PATHWAY TO A HEALTHIER CLIMATE AND IMPROVED WELL-BEING

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ABSTRACT

Decarbonization and the transition to zero-emissions have become critical priorities in the fight against climate change, particularly within the industrial and manufacturing sectors, which are among the largest contributors to global greenhouse gas emissions. Achieving zero emissions in these sectors is vital for the attainment of international climate targets, such as those outlined in the Paris Agreement. This review explores the strategies and technologies that industries and manufacturing plants are adopting to enhance decarbonization, including energy efficiency improvements, renewable energy integration, carbon capture and storage (CCS), and circular economy practices. Case studies of companies and sectors leading the way in decarbonization are highlighted to provide practical examples of the transition towards a zero-emissions economy.

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This paper also discusses the associated health and wellness benefits of reducing industrial emissions, as cleaner air and healthier ecosystems contribute to improved public health. Lastly, challenges to achieving zero emissions and future research directions are examined.

Keywords: Decarbonization, Zero Emissions, Environmental Sustainability, Cement, Energy Efficiency, Renewable Energy

Cite this Article: Daniel Edet Eyo, Adedolapo Olujuwon Adegbite, Elizabeth W. Salako, Ridwan Adebowale Yusuf, Faith Osaretin Osabuohien, Olasubomi Asuni, Taopheck Yusuf, Enhancing Decarbonization and Achieving Zero Emissions in Industries and Manufacturing Plants: A Pathway to A Healthier Climate and Improved Well-Being, International Journal of Mechanical Engineering and Technology (IJMET), 15(5), 2024, pp. 15-22.

https://iaeme.com/MasterAdmin/Journal_uploads/IJMET/VOLUME_15_ISSUE_5/IJMET_15_05_002.pdf

1. INTRODUCTION

Climate change is widely recognized as one of the most pressing global challenges of the 21st century, and industrial activity is a major driver of this phenomenon [1]. Industries and manufacturing plants contribute approximately 40% of global CO₂ emissions, primarily from the combustion of fossil fuels for energy and the release of emissions from industrial processes [2, 3]. To mitigate the adverse effects of climate change, decarbonization—the reduction of carbon dioxide (CO₂) emissions—is essential, particularly in high-emission industries such as steel, cement, and chemicals [4].

Achieving zero emissions in the industrial sector is not only critical for addressing climate change but also for improving public health and well-being. Reducing air pollution from industrial activities can lower the incidence of respiratory and cardiovascular diseases, improve ecosystem health, and reduce the economic burden of climate-related disasters. This paper reviews strategies for enhancing decarbonization in industries and manufacturing plants, focusing on energy efficiency, renewable energy, carbon capture, and circular economy approaches. Case studies are presented to illustrate successful implementation, and the paper concludes with a discussion of challenges and future opportunities [5-8].

2. STRATEGIES FOR ENHANCING DECARBONIZATION IN INDUSTRIES

2.1. Energy Efficiency Improvements

Energy efficiency is one of the most cost-effective and accessible methods for reducing carbon emissions in industries. By using energy more efficiently, manufacturing plants can lower their energy demand, reducing the need for fossil fuel-based power and cutting associated emissions. In the steel industry, energy efficiency can be improved through the use of high-efficiency electric arc furnaces (EAFs), which recycle scrap metal rather than relying on energy-intensive processes like blast furnaces [9, 10]. According to Zang Guiyan, et.al., electric arc furnaces use up to 75% less energy than traditional blast furnaces, leading to substantial reductions in CO₂ emissions [11].

Additionally, smart energy management systems, such as those powered by artificial intelligence (AI) and machine learning (ML), are enabling plants to monitor and optimize energy use in real-time. Sensors and advanced analytics help identify inefficiencies, allowing for targeted interventions that reduce energy waste [12]. In India, the cement industry has made significant strides in improving energy efficiency through the adoption of modern dry-process technology and waste heat recovery system.

This has resulted in a 20% reduction in energy consumption per ton of cement produced, contributing to an overall reduction in CO₂ emissions of approximately 12 million metric tons per year [13].

2.2. Renewable Energy Integration

Shifting from fossil fuel-based energy to renewable sources such as solar, wind, and hydropower is a cornerstone of decarbonization in industrial operations. The adoption of renewable energy in industries can significantly reduce greenhouse gas emissions and support the transition to a zero-emissions future [8]. Renewable electricity generation is crucial for decarbonizing sectors like aluminum and steel, which require large amounts of electricity [14]. In Norway, the aluminum manufacturer Hydro is pioneering the use of hydropower to run its production processes, reducing CO₂ emissions by approximately 50% compared to traditional coal-based power [15, 16]. Some industries are also integrating on-site renewable energy systems to power their operations. Solar photovoltaic (PV) panels and wind turbines are being installed at manufacturing plants to meet part or all of their electricity needs [17].

In the U.S., Tesla's Gigafactory in Nevada is one of the largest industrial plants powered primarily by renewable energy. The factory is equipped with solar panels that generate a significant portion of the plant's energy needs, helping Tesla achieve its goal of becoming a zero-emissions manufacturer. As of 2021, the Gigafactory's reliance on renewable energy has resulted in a 40% reduction in its carbon footprint compared to similar facilities [18, 19].

2.3. Carbon Capture, Utilization, and Storage (CCUS)

Carbon capture, utilization, and storage (CCUS) technology is essential for decarbonizing industries that are difficult to electrify or fully decarbonize through renewable energy alone, such as cement and steel production [20]. CCUS involves capturing CO₂ emissions from industrial processes and either utilizing them in other applications (e.g., for enhanced oil recovery or building materials) or storing them underground in geological formations. In the cement industry, CCUS can capture up to 90% of CO₂ emissions from production processes. HeidelbergCement, a global leader in the industry, is investing in CCUS technologies to reduce its carbon footprint [21, 22]. The company's Norway-based project, "Norcem Brevik," is on track to become the world's first full-scale cement plant equipped with CCUS, expected to capture 400,000 tons of CO₂ annually [21, 23].

2.4. Circular Economy Practices

The circular economy emphasizes reducing waste, recycling materials, and designing products for long-term use, which can contribute significantly to industrial decarbonization. By minimizing resource extraction and encouraging the reuse of materials, industries can reduce both direct and indirect carbon emissions. In the plastics industry, the adoption of a circular economy model is reducing emissions by promoting the recycling of plastics. Companies are developing closed-loop systems where plastic waste is collected, recycled, and reintroduced into the production cycle. This approach reduces the need for virgin plastic production, which is highly carbon-intensive [24, 25].

Steel is one of the most recycled materials globally, with more than 60% of new steel coming from recycled scrap [26]. The use of recycled steel reduces CO₂ emissions by 58%, as it avoids the energy-intensive process of mining and refining raw iron ore. ArcelorMittal, the world's largest steel producer, has embraced this model, committing to using 100% recycled steel by 2050 to achieve carbon neutrality [27].

3. CASE STUDIES: LEADING EXAMPLES OF DECARBONIZATION IN INDUSTRIES

3.1. The Danish Cement Industry: Decarbonization through Energy Efficiency and CCUS

Denmark's cement industry, led by Aalborg Portland, has been a pioneer in decarbonization efforts, focusing on improving energy efficiency and adopting CCUS technologies. The company has invested heavily in waste heat recovery, capturing excess heat from the cement production process and using it to generate electricity. This approach has reduced the plant's energy consumption by 15%, leading to significant emissions reductions [28]

According to Imbabi et al. (2012), the global consumption of cement from 1990 to 2010 and the expected growth up to 2050 are illustrated in Figure 1. Cement usage has steadily increased between 1990 and 2050, largely due to the rising need for infrastructure and housing in fast-growing economies like China and India [29].

Fig 1: Global cement production is to Timothy Millar, IIEE, Lund University [29]

3.2. Siemens' Smart Manufacturing Plants: Digitalization and Decarbonization

Siemens, a global leader in industrial manufacturing, has implemented cutting-edge digital technologies to enhance decarbonization across its manufacturing plants. By using AI, IoT (Internet of Things), and digital twins, Siemens has created "smart factories" that optimize energy consumption and reduce emissions [30]. One of Siemens' flagship projects, the Amberg Electronics Plant in Germany, uses digital twins to simulate production processes in a virtual environment, identifying inefficiencies and reducing energy use. This approach has led to a 30% reduction in the plant's energy consumption and a 20% reduction in CO₂ emissions [31]

4. THE HEALTH AND WELLNESS BENEFITS OF REDUCING INDUSTRIAL EMISSIONS

Industrial decarbonization efforts not only address climate change but also have profound benefits for public health. The burning of fossil fuels in industries and manufacturing plants is a major source of air pollution, which is linked to respiratory illnesses, cardiovascular diseases, and premature death. Reducing industrial emissions can lead to cleaner air, improved health outcomes, and reduced healthcare costs.

4.1. Air Quality Improvements

The shift toward renewable energy, energy efficiency, and CCUS in industries results in lower emissions of harmful pollutants such as sulfur dioxide (SO₂), nitrogen oxides (NO_x), and particulate matter (PM). These pollutants are major contributors to poor air quality, which has been shown to exacerbate asthma, chronic obstructive pulmonary disease (COPD), and other respiratory conditions.

Example: In China, where industrial activity is a significant source of air pollution, the adoption of cleaner production technologies and renewable energy has resulted in a 25% reduction in PM_{2.5} levels in key industrial regions over the past decade [32]. This improvement in air quality is associated with a decrease in respiratory and cardiovascular disease rates [33].

4.2. Reduced Healthcare Costs

By reducing industrial emissions, countries can lower the healthcare burden associated with pollution-related diseases. A study by the European Environment Agency found that industrial air pollution costs European countries approximately €430 billion annually in healthcare expenses and lost productivity [34]. Achieving zero emissions in industries could dramatically reduce these costs, freeing up resources for other public health initiatives.

4.3. Improved Well-Being and Quality of Life

Cleaner air and healthier ecosystems contribute to improved overall well-being. Communities living near industrial plants that adopt decarbonization technologies report higher quality of life due to reduced exposure to pollutants and a cleaner environment. Furthermore, the global transition toward sustainability can create new job opportunities in green industries, improving economic well-being and social equity [35].

5. CHALLENGES AND FUTURE DIRECTIONS

5.1. Technological and Financial Barriers

While significant progress has been made in decarbonizing industries, challenges remain. The high upfront costs of implementing advanced technologies such as CCUS, renewable energy systems, and AI-driven energy management can be prohibitive for small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs). Additionally, some industries, such as cement and steel, are difficult to fully decarbonize due to the energy-intensive nature of their production processes.

5.2. Policy and Regulatory Support

Governments play a crucial role in facilitating industrial decarbonization by providing policy frameworks, incentives, and regulations that encourage the adoption of clean technologies. Carbon pricing, emissions trading schemes, and subsidies for renewable energy are essential tools for driving emissions reductions. However, inconsistent policy frameworks across regions can create barriers to global progress.

5.3. Research and Development

Ongoing research and development (R&D) are essential to overcoming the technological limitations of decarbonization. Innovations in hydrogen production, advanced batteries, and CCUS technologies have the potential to revolutionize industries, making zero-emissions manufacturing more accessible and affordable. Increased investment in R&D, as well as collaboration between industry, government, and academia, will be crucial for achieving long-term decarbonization goals.

6. CONCLUSION

Decarbonizing industries and achieving zero emissions is essential for mitigating climate change and improving public health. By adopting energy efficiency improvements, integrating renewable energy, implementing CCUS, and embracing circular economy practices, industries can significantly reduce their carbon footprint and contribute to a healthier climate. Case studies from leading companies and sectors demonstrate that these strategies are not only feasible but also beneficial for business sustainability and public well-being.

As we move toward a future where zero-emissions industries are the norm, it is critical to address the challenges associated with the transition, including technological, financial, and policy barriers. With continued innovation, policy support, and collaboration, the industrial sector can play a key role in achieving global climate goals and ensuring a healthier, more sustainable future for all.

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Citation: Daniel Edet Eyo, Adedolapo Olujuwon Adegbite, Elizabeth W. Salako, Ridwan Adebowale Yusuf, Faith Osaretin Osabuohien, Olasubomi Asuni, Taopheek Yusuf, Enhancing Decarbonization and Achieving Zero Emissions in Industries and Manufacturing Plants: A Pathway to A Healthier Climate and Improved Well-Being, International Journal of Mechanical Engineering and Technology (IJMET), 15(5), 2024, pp. 15-22

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